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EFFECT OF DILUENTS ON PHARMACEUTICAL-TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE PARACETAMOL TABLETS

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Fillers are a very important group of excipients in tablets obtained by direct compression, as they make up the largest share of the mass of the tablet. Their role is to achieve the practical size of the pharmaceutical dosage form. In this study, the influence of the choice and share of fillers on the mechanical properties of paracetamol tablets and on the dissolution profile of paracetamol was examined.

Four formulations of paracetamol tablets (F1, F2, F3 and F4) were made using a laboratory exciter machine. Each of the formulations contained 7% paracetamol, 0.5% magnesium stearate (lubricant) and 4% sodium starch glycolate (disintegrant). Lactose and microcrystalline cellulose were used as fillers which accounted for 88.5% of the tablet weight. The share of lactose in F1 was 0%, in F2 17.7%, in F3 70.8% and in F4 88.5%, while the remaining share of fillers was microcrystalline cellulose. Methods for determining the bulk angle and bulk and tapping densities were used to test the flowability of the tableting mass. Examination of the dissolution profile was performed in accordance with the 10th European Pharmacopoeia, with paddle type apparatus and phosphate buffer, for 60 minutes. The concentration of paracetamol in the samples was determined via UV/Vis spectrophotometer. Friability, disintegration, resistance to crushing, uniformity of mass and uniformity of content were also tested in accordance with the 10th European Pharmacopoeia.

Examination of dissolution profiles showed that all 4 formulations meet the requirements of the 10th European Pharmacopoeia for immediate release tablets. The difference in release rate was observed only in the first 5 min: F1 released the most (91.95%) and F4 the least (71.76%). These results were consistent with hardness and disintegration tests - formulations with a higher lactose content showed greater hardness and longer disintegration times. Mass variation testing showed that none of the 4 formulations met the requirements of the 10th European Pharmacopoeia, which is related to the poor flowability of the tested tableting masses. The best flowability was observed in the tabulation mass for F3.

The optimal pharmaceutical-technological characteristics were obtained in formulation with a mixture of lactose and microcrystalline cellulose as fillers, where the share of lactose is higher. In order to improve the flowability of the mixture, the tableting mass can be converted into granules, or a silica-type agent can be used.

Keywords: Lactose, Microcrystalline Cellulose, Excipients, Dissolution Profile.

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